

Making Few-shot Object Detection Simpler and Less Frustrating

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Abstract. Few-shot object detection is useful in order to extend object detection capabilities in media production and archiving applications with specific object classes of interest for a particular organization or production context. While recent approaches for few-shot object detection have advanced the state of the art, they still do not fully meet the requirements of practical workflows, e.g., in media production and archiving. In these applications, annotated samples for novel classes are drawn from different data sources, they differ in numbers and it may be necessary to add a new class quickly to cover the requirements of a specific production. In contrast, current frameworks for few-shot object detection typically assume a static dataset, which is split into the base and novel classes. We propose a toolchain to facilitate training for few-shot object detection, which takes care of data preparation when using heterogeneous training data and setup of training steps. The toolchain also creates annotation files to use combined data sets as new base models, which facilitates class-incremental training. We also integrated the toolchain with an annotation UI.

Keywords: few-shot learning, object detection, data preparation, annotation tool, incremental training

1 Introduction

Few-shot object detection is useful in order to extend object detection capabilities in sourcing (e.g., annotation of feeds of raw material) or archiving with specific object classes of interest for a particular organization or production context. If the object class of interest is not covered by a publicly available dataset (or license conditions do not permit the use of such a dataset), the labeling of a large amount of training samples is typically not feasible. Few-shot object detection enables training with an amount of samples that can be labeled by a single user with acceptable effort. While the resulting classifier is likely to achieve lower performance than one trained on a thousands of samples, it may still enable detection of otherwise uncovered classes. In addition, detection results (possibly in combination with object tracking) can be used to mine data for retraining a classifier on a larger set.

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production. In contrast, current frameworks for few-shot object detection typically assume a static dataset, which is split into the base and novel classes. In this paper, we propose a training toolchain that extends the widely used approach “Frustratingly simple few-shot object detection” by Wang et al. [6] in order to facilitate the training of few-shot learning models and enable class-incremental training. In addition, we integrate the toolchain with an annotation user interface (UI). The tools described in this paper are available as open source software.

In Section 2 we provide more details about the motivation of this work and the choice of the few-shot learning framework. In Section 3 we present the toolchain and discuss its integration with the annotation UI in Section 4. Section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Motivation and Context

This work focuses on few-shot object detection, serving use cases in annotating incoming material in media production or for archiving. We can observe three main aspects, where the setup of benchmarking problems (and thus the methods described in literature, as well as the existing implementations) deviate from the practical requirements of using few-shot object detection in media use cases:

- The typical setup of the problem is posed as n -way k -shot, i.e. a problem with n classes and k samples per shot. However, in practice the number of samples per class that are provided may differ.
- There is no fixed predefined dataset, but the set of base classes will contain a mixture of third party and maybe own data for some classes, while the novel classes are mined from own or third party media content (e.g., web sites). Thus the concept of a dataset is fluid, and the available data will evolve over time.
- Classes may need to be added incrementally, which requires creating balanced training sets, but approaches should aim to keep the training effort low. This again means that there is no fixed notion of a dataset, but it needs to be updated on the fly.

Taking these aspects into consideration, we decided to focus on metric or contrastive rather than meta-learning type of approaches. In addition, we are interested to use a framework, which can be applied to object detection as well as segmentation. Methods of interest are thus Karlinsky et al. [3], which uses FPN to create an object detection pipeline using metric learning. Classification is done using a different method for pretrained classes, while few-shot learning is done with FPN (in the DCN variant) instead. Singh et al.[5] propose to train a generic object detector on ImageNet, sampling positive and negative candidate regions. This approach is suitable for generic object detection, beyond the originally trained classes. An approach based on meta-features and learning reweighting of those features is proposed by Kang et al. [2]. A recent work [6] applies fine-tuning only to region proposal and classification layers on a data set consisting of many base class and few new class samples while fixing the feature extraction part of the network, using Faster R-CNN [4] as a backbone. It has been shown that it can outperform meta-learning approaches [6].

We are interested in a framework that can potentially also be used with single-stage detectors and extended to support segmentation. We thus use the work of Wang et al. [6] as the basis of our work. This work proposes a two-stage fine-tuning (TFA) approach. A backbone model such as Faster R-CNN is trained on the base classes using a standard training approach. Then the last layer of the model is extended to include the novel classes, and the new weights are randomly initialized. Fine-tuning of the model is performed by training with a dataset formed from k samples from each of the base classes, and the samples of the novel classes. Both the classification and bounding box regression branch are trained using this balanced dataset, but the feature extraction part of the model is not updated. In addition, the fine-tuning step uses a cosine similarity based classifier, which results in improved accuracy for the novel classes and lower decrease for the base classes compared to an FC-based classifier. As an alternative to randomly initializing the new weights, a separate training step for the last layer can be performed with the new classes, and the results can be used to initialize the weights of the novel classes in the combined model.

3 Training toolchain

We have extended the framework of Wang et al. [6] with a tool that dynamically generates datasets and drives the training process. The tool aims to facilitate the training process and to enable incremental training. The code of training toolchain is available at <https://github.com/wbailer/few-shot-object-detection>.

3.1 Facilitating training

We aim to drive the few-shot training process by the available data in the process, so that few-shot training can be deployed as a service to be integrated in a media analysis toolchain. The expected input to such a service are a set of samples and corresponding annotations, as well as a small configuration file, which describes the base model to be used, the data locations and whether all or just some classes of the new data shall be used for training. The user may supply separate datasets for training and validation, or the tool can create splits at a defined ratio. The samples and annotations may be entirely user supplied (i.e., manually annotated), or may result from a semi-automatic process. Such a process may use weakly supervised object detection and tracking, where the user only coarsely identifies the object in one frame and provides a class label, but the bounding boxes (or masks) are determined automatically by segmenting the object throughout a sequence.

In particular, the tool covers the following steps:

- Determine the base and novel classes from the provided annotations. For both the base and novel classes only a subset of classes may be actually used in the training. This provides more flexibility in the process, and is also required to support incremental training without splitting the source annotation files.
- Determine how many instances are available, and set up the k -shot n -way problem accordingly, with $k = \min(k_1, \dots, k_n)$.

- If needed, create the training and validation splits of the dataset.
- Prepare model structures for novel only training and fine-tuning of the combined base+novel model by adjusting the layer sizes to match the number of classes in the different sets. This includes scaling up the number of classes arbitrarily, which goes beyond the current functionality of the framework, that assumes a split of fixed number of classes.
- If the number of samples strongly varies, set up multiple training problems to make best use of the data. This is implemented by specifying a factor q , which causes a split if half of the classes have q times more samples than the one with the fewest samples, i.e., $\text{median}(k_1, \dots, k_n) \geq q \min(k_1, \dots, k_n)$.

The tool currently supports annotations in COCO format¹. However, this does not mean that COCO is required as a base model, as long as the annotations are provided in this format. The training tool has been tested with a pretrained base model containing 60 COCO classes (from the model zoo provided by the authors of the few-shot learning framework²), and adding a subset of 20 novel classes selected from the LVIS dataset. This example training configuration is provided with the code (under `configs/custom_datasets`).

3.2 Towards incremental training

The proposed tool can also be used for incremental training of new classes. The training tool provides as additional output the dataset annotation files that are required to use the resulting model as a base model. Similar to the splitting of the training step in case of unequal number of samples, also different incremental training steps can use different values for k . These files can be directly used as base models in the next training iteration.

However, due to the two-stage fine-tuning (TFA) approach in the framework, the fine-tuning step is run for all classes, including the base classes and of novel classes from previous iterations. This step is typically computationally more expensive than the training process for novel classes, in particular, if the number of classes in an incremental training step is small. Thus the runtime saving in incremental training will be less than the fraction of the added classes to all novel classes. A recent paper proposes to avoid running this fine-tuning step after incremental training [1], but at the expense of training an instance feature embedding, and requiring access to these features at inference stage.

4 Integration with Annotation UI

In order to facilitate the creation of the necessary annotations and configuration files, we decided to integrate the proposed toolchain with an annotation UI. We chose the

¹ <https://cocodataset.org/#format-data>

² https://github.com/ucbdrive/few-shot-object-detection/blob/master/docs/MODEL_ZOO.md

Fig. 1. Example of annotating samples for few-shot annotation.

open source tool MakeSense³ as a basis. It is a rather lightweight tool written using TypeScript and React, that runs in the browser and does not require image upload to a server. The tool supports point, line, rectangle and polygon annotations, and can export them in common formats, including COCO. A screenshot of an example project is shown in Figure 1.

When creating a new project, we have added a dialog that collects the basic information about the few-shot training task (see Figure 2). Then the user selects the set of images to work on, and defines the labels for the novel classes. The base model is selected from a fixed set of preconfigured base models, as the model file, the annotation files and the subset of included classes need to match. Models resulting from few-shot training and used as base models for incremental training can be added here (in the current version, this step is not automated and needs to be done manually).

Once the user is done with the annotation, the configuration for few-shot training can be exported. This export will store the annotation file (which is split into the training and validation sets automatically), the script calling for the toolchain described in Section 3 and the configuration file needed by this script. The user needs to set via environment variable or in this script the location of the local installation of the few-shot learning framework. As the annotation UI runs in the browser, it cannot directly start the training toolchain, this would require running a local server that could be called from the TypeScript code, and would then run the training tool. However, starting the script manually is probably easier than requiring the installation of an additional component.

The modified version of the annotation tool is available at <https://github.com/wbailer/make-sense>.

³ <https://www.makesense.ai/>

Fig. 2. Dialog for configuring few-shot training.

5 Conclusion

In this paper, we have proposed a toolchain to facilitate training for few-shot object detection, which takes care of data preparation when using heterogeneous training data and setup of training steps. The toolchain also creates annotation files to use combined data sets as new base models, which facilitates class-incremental training. We integrated the toolchain with an annotation UI, allowing the user to perform the necessary configuration and annotation in the browser. Both the toolchain extending a widely used few-shot learning framework and the extended annotation UI are available as open source software.

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